

DETERMINATION OF THE STRAIN FIELD AROUND AN INTERLAMINAR CRACK USING MOIRE INTERFEROMETRY

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ABSTRACT

The high frequency moire interferometry is employed to measure the deformations near an interlaminar crack in graphite/epoxy composites. The measured displacements near the crack tip region are used to determine the order of the stress singularity of a crack in both (90) and (0) laminates. The experimentally determined stress singularity values are then compared with the theoretical predictions and the results are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a large amount of research work on the stress analysis of interlaminar cracks has been published [1-5]. Some of these studies are concerned with mechanisms of failure on the micro level while others focus on the macro behavior to obtain average fracture properties. Regardless of the micro or macro approach, a convenient assumption often used in the analysis is the existence of a "sharp" crack, that is, a discontinuity with zero radius of curvature at the tip. As a result of this assumption, a singular stress field similar to that in metals (except that the order of singularity is different) has been obtained for composites containing an interlaminar discontinuity. However, unlike metals a composite may not develop such a "sharp" crack on the micro scale since it is composed of many fibers in an embedded matrix. At the tip of an interlaminar crack there may be multiple subcracks formed or bridged together depending on the specific fiber geometry and ply orientations. Thus, it is important to understand the actual strain field near the tip of an interlaminar crack before an appropriate fracture theory can be developed for composites.

In this paper, the crack-tip deformations of graphite/epoxy composites are measured using the moire interferometry technique [6-8]. The associated strain fields are obtained from the displacement fringes using a numerical differentiation. The order of stress singularity of a crack is determined from the measured opening displacements near the crack tip. The experimental results are compared with the analytical predictions and the differences between the two methods are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The graphite/epoxy AS4/3501-6 composite with (90)₈₀ layup orientation (80 plies) is used in the study. The prepreg tape was cured in a heated press per the step curing schedule suggested by the manufacturer. The cured graphite/epoxy panel is then machined into 10.795 mm (0.425 in.) wide x 10.795 mm (0.425 in.) thick x 34.036 mm (1.34 in.) long V-shape notched specimens (see Figure 1). The fracture specimen

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is loaded by a round bar at the notch end in a static test machine. Both the axial displacement, u , and the applied load, P , are recorded continuously using an xy plotter. A typical load-displacement curve for the (90)80 specimens are shown in Figure 3.

The crack-tip deformations are measured by a moire interferometry technique. A diffraction grating of dimensions 10.795 mm (0.425 in.) x 34.036 mm (1.34 in.) with 1200 lines/mm is used for the entire specimen region. The complete moire interferometry setup and optical paths are illustrated in Fig. 2. The experimental setup consists of a load frame, a 35 mw He-Ne laser, a camera, and various optical components mounted on a holographic platform. Both the u and v displacements are measured using a specially designed moire fixture [7,8]. The resulting fringe patterns are scanned and digitized in a Macintosh II system. These displacement data are then differentiated numerically to obtain the appropriate strain components.

CRACK-TIP DEFORMATIONS

Using the above procedure, the moire fringes representing deformation contours around an interlaminar crack in (90)80 laminates have been obtained. Figure 4a shows the resulting v displacement fringe pattern for an applied load of 369.4 N (83 lbs). The strain components are calculated by differentiating the measured displacement field. A typical strain component $\partial v/\partial y$ associated with the displacement contour in Figure 4a is shown in Figure 4b. The u -displacement component in the x -direction and the corresponding strain field $\partial u/\partial x$ are given in Figure 5a and 5b, respectively. It is observed that an extremely high strain concentration occurs near the crack-tip region.

The deformations obtained by the moire interferometry are then used to determine the order of the stress singularity of an interlaminar crack in the (90)80 laminates. Table 1 summarizes the measured opening displacements, v , at various points along the crack surface. These data are also plotted in Figure 6. It is noted that, outside the crack-tip region, the displacement, v , is proportional to the distance, r ; that is, the far-field opening displacements are mainly caused by a rigid-body rotation of the crack surface. However, within the crack-tip region, the v - r relationship is nonlinear and is dominated by the singular behavior at the crack tip. In order to study the strength of this singularity, the v -displacements near the crack tip ($r/a \leq 0.0189$) are plotted in Figure 7a in a log-log format. It is seen that these experimental data fall into a straight line with slope m equal to 0.649. This compares with the theoretical prediction of $m=0.500$ from the stress analysis of cracks in orthotropic materials.

In addition, the u -displacements in the x -direction are shown in Figure 7b. Similar to the v -component, the crack-tip u -displacements can be best fitted by a straight line with a slope of 0.658. Thus, the order of the crack-tip singularity measured by this experiment based on either the v or the u displacement in the (90)80 specimen is larger than the theoretical value. The difference between the experimental results and the theoretical prediction may be due to the different crack-tip conditions at the micro scale. A sharp crack with zero radius of curvature is usually assumed in a fracture analysis. While this ideal crack-tip condition is attainable in metals, it is unlikely to prevail in composites of the 90 deg. orientation. On the micro scale, multiple subcracks can possibly occur around the fiber/matrix interface near the tip of a crack in composites. As a result, the displacement fields can be different from those predicted based on the assumption of a sharp crack. In fact, further experimental studies show that the order of the stress singularity in the (0)80 specimen is 0.489, which is much closer to the theoretical result. The crack tip conditions in (90)80 and (0)80 laminates are different due to the inherent fiber/matrix geometry at the micro level.

CONCLUSIONS

The high frequency moire interferometry has been employed to determine the whole-field deformations of an interlaminar crack in composite laminates. Both the u and v displacement fringes and the associated strain fields have been obtained for the graphite/epoxy (90)80 specimens. Using the measured crack-tip displacements, the order of the stress singularity for an interlaminar crack in an orthotropic material has been determined experimentally. The results show that the stress singularity value is dependent upon the micro crack-tip condition. The order of the singularity of an interlaminar crack is found to be 0.65 for the (90)80 specimen and 0.49 for the (0)80 laminates.

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Table 1 The Measured Crack Opening Displacements

<u>V (mm)</u>	<u>R (mm)</u>	<u>V (mm)</u>	<u>R (mm)</u>
0.00021	0.00318	0.01666	2.08029
0.00042	0.00953	0.01750	2.19145
0.00063	0.02000	0.01833	2.31849
0.00083	0.03900	0.01916	2.41377
0.00125	0.06000	0.02000	2.50905
0.00167	0.09900	0.02083	2.62021
0.00208	0.12800	0.02166	2.73137
0.00250	0.17468	0.02250	2.82664
0.00292	0.21120	0.02333	2.92192
0.00333	0.25500	0.02416	3.03308
0.00375	0.30172	0.02500	3.12836
0.00417	0.35412	0.02583	3.23952
0.00458	0.40494	0.02666	3.33482
0.00500	0.46052	0.02750	3.44596
0.00542	0.52086	0.02833	3.55714
0.00583	0.58756	0.02916	3.65242
0.00625	0.65743	0.03000	3.73182
0.00667	0.73048	0.03083	3.82170
0.00708	0.80194	0.03166	3.92238
0.00750	0.88928	0.03249	4.01766
0.00792	0.94486	0.03333	4.11294
0.00833	1.00045	0.03417	4.20822
0.00916	1.09573	0.03500	4.30350
0.01000	1.20689	0.03583	4.39878
0.01083	1.31805	0.03667	4.47818
0.01166	1.44509	0.03750	4.55758
0.01250	1.54037	0.03833	4.66874
0.01333	1.63565	0.03917	4.76420
0.01416	1.76269	0.04000	4.85390
0.01500	1.87385	0.04083	4.93870
0.01583	1.96913	0.04167	5.03399

Fig. 1 The V-notched fracture specimen

Fig. 2 The experimental setup for moiré interferometry

Fig. 3 Load-axial displacement curve

Fig. 4 The V-displacement fringe pattern and the strain field

Fig. 5 The U-displacement fringe pattern and the strain field

Fig. 6 The opening V-displacements along the crack surface

(a) $\log V$ vs. $\log r$

(b) $\log U$ vs. $\log r$

Fig. 7 Deformations near the crack tip